

KARAKALPAK NATIONAL CULTURE IS THE MAIN VALUE OF THE
KARAKALPAK PEOPLE

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Culture (from Latin cultura – cultivation, later – upbringing, education, development, veneration) is a concept that has a huge number of meanings various areas of human life. Culture is the subject of study of philosophy, cultural studies, history, art, linguistics (ethnolinguistics), political science, ethnology, psychosology, economics, pedagogy, etc.

National art has always been of great importance throughout the entire historical past. It has always reflected the history and culture of the people. With the independence of the Republic, the process of reviving the traditional national art from such types as embroidery, carpet weaving and so on began.

Attention to the cultural heritage of our ancestors developed in the late 18th – early 19th centuries. If we look at our national heritage, we see our past as a reflection of the lifestyle of our ancestors. One of these heritages is the national costumes of the.

The national costume, in which the richest traditions of Karakalpak arts and crafts were embodied to the fullest extent, is an expression of the aesthetic ideals of the people, ensures the transfer from generation, the spiritual historical experience. The Karakalpak costume has original and unique features. With the same beginning of Karakalpak women's clothing is used popular due to the rich color range embroidery. Embroidery is associated with a huge world of ornamental images that has evolved over the centuries. Therefore, at present there is a need for the revival and development of the art of embroidery using folk traditions.

Karakalpak national clothes have retained their archaic features. It conveys the specifics of the Karakalpak people, reflects culture, spirituality and history. Karakalpak national costumes are very bright, beautiful, comfortable, unique and are part of the rich cultural traditions and lifestyle of the people. In the cities it is no longer possible to meet people in national dress, today it is worn for traditional festive events, but in the countryside it still serves as part of both everyday and weekend attire.

Karakalpak women's clothing: shirt-dress (koylek), camisole, sleeveless jacket (zhensiz), robe, headwear (kiymeshek, saukele, skullcap,). All Karakalpak women owned the rules of cutting and sewing. The most rich and colorful was the costume of young women who preferred red fabrics. Elderly women wore clothes made of white and dark fabrics. The entire ensemble of the women's costume was distinguished by calmness and restrained beauty. The traditional women's costume merged with the man, ideally matching his mental make-up, character, occupations and living space. The complex complex of the traditional costume combined utility, beauty and spirituality.

The ancient dress Kok Koilek (Khalkaly Koilek, Kestel Koilek) with a continuous rich ornamentation on the chest has amazing beauty and perfection. A cook koilek was sewn from blue homespun cloth. The cut is loose, straight, without seams in the shoulders. Sidewalls with small slits at the bottom, the collar is high, standing, on the chest there is a vertical slit for the gate. The sleeves are wide and long with gussets. The front of the dress is almost entirely embroidered with multi-colored silk threads. The pattern is geometric, arranged in oblique rows and composed of rhombuses with horn-shaped processes at the vertical corners. Below are "hanging" stylized images that are called syrğa nagys, reminiscent of earrings. The kok koilek ornament bears the common name sauyt nagys - chain mail pattern. This gives grounds to assume that in the selected kok koileks, the traditions of the attire of warriors of the Sako-Massaget clans, sung in the Karakalpak folk epic "Kyrk kyz", found a response. Rows of ornamental stripes of diamond-shaped figures on the chest vaguely resemble armor, chain mail. In addition, Kok Koylek has no analogues among other kindred peoples.

The semantic and aesthetic center of the women's costume was the elegant saukele headdress with various ornaments. The Karakalpak saukele is a soft round hat with earflaps made of felt, covered with red cloth and variously decorated with corals and other stones. Rows of coral beads completely covered individual sections of the dress. At the back, the headdress had a blade descending to the neck, from under which a narrow embroidered strip of halaka fabric fell below the waist, and sometimes up to the knees. The earmuffs are decorated with corals strung on silk threads, sewn in thick rows onto two narrow figured strips of red cloth, parallel to each other (one is along the edge of the earmuffs, the second is slightly retreating from it). Small metal plaques of various shapes, decorated with coral and other stones, are sewn between the corals (on the sides of the kyran, on the frontal part of the jig, etc.).

By studying traditional clothes, we study our ancient history. Clothing indicated the social status of a woman. In women's clothing, the national identity and the precious heritage of the people are clearly expressed. And we need to preserve our precious tradition and improve the national clothes of the Karakalpaks and, by changing their design, introduce them as modern clothes for everyday life, so that national clothes can be worn not only on holidays and everyday life. Thus, we need to innovate in the development of design and fashion in clothing.

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